

Solution of Second Order Initial- Boundary Value Problems of Partial Integro-Differential Equations by using a New Transform: Mahgoub Transform

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ABSTRACT

The partial integro-differential equations (PIDEs) have many possible applications in areas like mathematics, physics and engineering. Therefore, we develop a new transform, which was proposed by Mahgoub [1], for solving second order initial-boundary value problems (IBVPs) of PIDEs. This transform is characterized by its simplicity of use.

Key words: Integral transform, Mahgoub transform, Boundary value problems, Partial integro-differential equations.

INTRODUCTION

Let's look at the second order IBVP of PIDE as follows:

$$u_{tt}(x,t) = u_{xx}(x,t) + \lambda \int_0^t k(t-s)u(x,s)ds + g(x,t), \quad x \in \Omega, t \in J \quad (1)$$

with initial (IC) and boundary (BC) conditions

$$u(x,0) = u_0(x), \quad u_t(x,0) = u_{0t}(x), \quad x \in [a,b]$$

$$u(a,t) = h(t), \quad u(b,t) = l(t), \quad t \in [0,T],$$

where $u_{tt}(x,t) = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2}$, $u_{xx}(x,t) = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$, λ is constant, $g(x,t)$ is known function and $k(t-s)$ is given kernel function.

Several methods for solving PIDEs are given [2-9].

In this paper, we present application Mahgoub transform for solving second order IBVPs of PIDEs.

APPLICATION MAHGOUB TRANSFORM TO SECOND ORDER IBVPS OF PIDEs

Recently, a new transform was proposed by Mahgoub [1] in 2016. He define the function A for $t \geq 0$ as

$$A = \left\{ f(t) : \exists M, k_1, k_2 > 0, |f(t)| < Me^{\frac{|t|}{k_j}} \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where M, k_1, k_2 are constants and M is a finite.

The operator $M\{f(t)\}$ is given as

$$M \{f(t)\} = H(v) = v \int_0^{\infty} f(t)e^{-vt} dt, k_1 \leq v \leq k_2. \quad (3)$$

FACT: (LINEARITY PROPERTY)

Let $f(t)$ and $g(t)$ are functions whose Mahgoub transform exists, then

$$M \{c_1 f(t) + c_2 g(t)\} = c_1 M \{f(t)\} + c_2 M \{g(t)\}, \text{ where } c_1 \text{ and } c_2 \text{ are constants.}$$

Proof:
$$\begin{aligned} M \{c_1 f(t) + c_2 g(t)\} &= v \int_0^{\infty} [c_1 f(t) + c_2 g(t)] e^{-vt} dt \\ &= v c_1 \int_0^{\infty} f(t) e^{-vt} dt + v c_2 \int_0^{\infty} g(t) e^{-vt} dt \\ &= c_1 M \{f(t)\} + c_2 M \{g(t)\}. \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Theorem: Let $f(t)$ and $g(t)$ are functions and given by $M \{f(t)\} = F(v)$ and $M \{g(t)\} = G(v)$ then

$$M \{f(t) g(t)\} = \frac{1}{2} F(v) G(v).$$

Proof: We choose $F(v) = v \int_0^{\infty} f(w) e^{-vw} dw$ and $G(v) = v \int_0^{\infty} g(l) e^{-vl} dl$, then

$$F(v) G(v) = v^2 \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} f(w) g(l) e^{-v(w+l)} dl dw$$

Let $w + l = t \Rightarrow dw = dt$, then

$$\begin{aligned} F(v) G(v) &= v^2 \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^t f(w) g(t-w) e^{-vt} dl dt \\ &= v M \{f(t) g(t)\} \end{aligned}$$

So

$$\frac{1}{v} F(v) G(v) = M \{f(t) g(t)\}. \blacksquare$$

Now, we going to solve (1) by taking $M \{ \}$ on both sides

$$M \{u_{tt}(x, t)\} = M \left\{ u_x(x, t) + \lambda \int_0^t k(t-s) u(x, s) ds + g(x, t) \right\}.$$

By using linearity property, we have

$$M \{u_{tt}(x, t)\} = M \{u_x(x, t)\} + \lambda M \left\{ \int_0^t k(t-s) u(x, s) ds \right\} + M \{g(x, t)\}.$$

From Mahgoub transform formula, it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} v \int_0^{\infty} e^{-vt} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2}(x, t) dt &= v \int_0^{\infty} e^{-vt} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}(x, t) dt + \lambda \frac{1}{v} (\bar{k}(v) H(x, v)) + \bar{g}(x, v). \\ \Rightarrow v^2 H(x, v) - v^2 u(x, 0) - v u_t(x, 0) &= \frac{d}{dx} H(x, v) + \lambda \frac{1}{v} (\bar{k}(v) H(x, v)) + \bar{g}(x, v), \end{aligned}$$

where $H(x, v) = M \{u(x, t)\}$, $\bar{k}(v) = M \{k(t-s)\}$, and $\bar{g}(x, v) = M \{g(x, t)\}$.

By substituting IC into above equation, then the solution becomes

$$v^2 H(x, v) - v^2 u_0 - v u_{t_0}(x, 0) = \frac{d}{dx} H(x, v) + \lambda \frac{1}{v} (\bar{k}(v) H(x, v)) + \bar{g}(x, v).$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} H(x, v) + \lambda \frac{1}{v} (\bar{k}(v) H(x, v)) - v^2 H(x, v) = \bar{g}(x, v) - v^2 u_0 + v u_{t_0}(x, 0).$$

This will give linear first order ODE as

$$\frac{d}{dx} H(x, v) + \left(\frac{\lambda}{v^2} - v^2 \right) H(x, v) = \bar{g}(x, v) - v^2 u_0 + v u_{t_0}(x, 0).$$

We can easily solve this type of ODEs and then find inverse Mahgoub transform.

EXAMPLE

Consider the IBVP [5]

$$u_{tt} = u_x + 2 \int_0^t (t-s) u(x, s) ds - 2e^x, \quad (4)$$

with IC: $u(x, 0) = e^x$, $u_t(x, 0) = 0$.

$$\text{BC: } u(0, t) = \cos t.$$

To solve (4), take Mahgoub transform on both sides

$$M \{u_{tt}\} = M \left\{ u_x + 2 \int_0^t (t-s) u(x, s) ds - 2e^x \right\}. \quad (5)$$

By using linearity property, we get

$$M \{u_{tt}\} = M \{u_x\} + 2M \left\{ \int_0^t (t-s) u(x, s) ds \right\} - 2e^x M \{1\}. \quad (6)$$

From Mahgoub transform formula, we have

$$v^2 H(x, v) - v^2 u(x, 0) - v u_t(x, 0) = H_x(x, v) + \frac{2}{v^2} (H(x, v)) - 2e^x. \quad (7)$$

By substituting IC into (7), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} v^2 H(x, v) - v^2 e^x &= H_x(x, v) + \frac{2}{v^2} (H(x, v)) - 2e^x. \\ \Rightarrow H_x(x, v) - v^2 H(x, v) + \frac{2}{v^2} (H(x, v)) + v^2 e^x - 2e^x &= 0. \\ \Rightarrow H_x(x, v) + \left(\frac{2}{v^2} - v^2 \right) H(x, v) &= (2 - v^2) e^x. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

This will give linear first order ODE as

$$\frac{dH(x, v)}{dx} + \left(\frac{2}{v^2} - v^2 \right) H(x, v) = (2 - v^2) e^x. \quad (9)$$

We can use integration factor $\mu = e^{\int (\frac{2}{v^2} - v^2) dx}$ to solve (9).

Therefore

$$\bar{H}(x, v) = \frac{\int \mu(x) \left((2 - v^2) e^x \right) dx + c}{\mu(x)}. \quad (10)$$

The solution of (10) is

$$\bar{H}(x, v) = \frac{v^2}{1 + v^2} e^x + c e^{-\left(\frac{2}{v^2} - v^2 \right) x}. \quad (11)$$

Substitute $u(x, 0) = e^x$ and $u_t(x, 0) = 0$ into (11), then $c = 0$.

So, we now have

$$\bar{H}(x, v) = \frac{v^2}{1+v^2} e^x. \quad (12)$$

From the inverse Mahgoub transform, the solution is then

$$H(x, v) = e^x \cos t. \quad (13)$$

Fig. 1 The graph of $H(x,t)$

CONCLUSION

Mahgoub transform is characterized by its simplicity of use. Also, it is accurate and efficient technique for finding solution IBVPs of PIDEs.

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